

Novel evolutionary insights on the interactions of the *Holosporales* (*Alphaproteobacteria*) with eukaryotic hosts from comparative genomics

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Abstract

Holosporales are an alphaproteobacterial order engaging in obligate and complex associations with eukaryotes, in particular protists. The functional and evolutionary features of those interactions are still largely undisclosed. Here, we sequenced the genomes of two members of the species *Bealeia paramacronuclearis* (*Holosporales*, *Holosporaceae*) intracellularly associated with the ciliate protist *Paramecium*, which resulted in high correspondence. Consistent with the short-branched early-divergent phylogenetic position, *Bealeia* presents a larger functional repertoire than other *Holosporaceae*, comparable to those of other *Holosporales* families, particularly for energy metabolism and motility. Our analyses indicate that different *Holosporales* likely experienced at least partly autonomous genome reduction and adaptation to host interactions, for example regarding dependence on host biotin driven by multiple independent horizontal acquisitions of transporters. Among *Alphaproteobacteria*, this is reminiscent of the convergently evolved *Rickettsiales*, which however appear more diverse, possibly due to a probably more ancient origin. We identified in *Bealeia* and other *Holosporales* the plasmid-encoded putative genetic determinants of R-bodies, which may be involved in a killer trait towards symbiont-free hosts. While it is not clear whether these genes are ancestral or recently horizontally acquired, an intriguing and peculiar role of R-bodies is suggested in the evolution of the interactions of multiple *Holosporales* with their hosts.

INTRODUCTION

Multiple phylogenetically diverse bacteria can establish long-term interactions with diverse eukaryotic hosts (Husnik et al., 2021; McFall-Ngai et al., 2013). Some shared evolutionary trends may be found among stably host-associated bacteria, in particular the loss of genes that have become redundant and/or no more necessary, typically leading to even drastic genome reduction, and eventually to dependence on the host (Bennett & Moran, 2015; Moran et al., 2008; Wernegreen, 2012).

Long-known and fairly well-studied examples are multiple cases of nutritional mutualists, in which distinct

free-living ancestors have convergently evolved towards comparable lifestyles (Sandström et al., 2001) experiencing marked genome reduction (even to the 100–200 Kb range) (Moran & Bennett, 2014). These processes are governed by the nutritional requirements of hosts with unbalanced diets, such as phytophagous or blood-feeding arthropods in the most thoroughly characterized cases (Buysse et al., 2021; Moran et al., 2008).

Some wide and ancient (over 1 bya) bacterial lineages, such as *Rickettsiales*, *Legionellales* and *Chlamydiae*, have been engaging associations with eukaryotes across extremely long evolutionary times

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(Dharamshi et al., 2020; Hugoson et al., 2022; Wang & Luo, 2021), and show more complex and varying traits. Each of those unrelated lineages encompasses a wide diversity of typically intracellular bacteria (or endosymbionts) associated with a variety of eukaryotic hosts, in particular, protists (Castelli et al., 2016; Collingro et al., 2020; Duron et al., 2018). While typically host-dependent, they are frequently able to perform horizontal transfer even between distantly related hosts. Their genomic and functional reduction is generally less pronounced than in nutritional mutualists. Specifically, they possess a diverse set of molecules involved in the active modulation of the interactions with the hosts, including secretion systems, secreted effectors, and surface adhesins/invasins (Betts-Hampikian & Fields, 2010; Gillespie et al., 2014; Renvoisé et al., 2011). Accordingly, these bacteria were collectively termed ‘professional symbionts’ (Husnik et al., 2021).

Evolutionary trends among professional symbionts are only partly understood, and, besides well-studied cases such as pathogens (e.g., *Rickettsia*, *Chlamydia*, *Legionella*) (Chauhan & Shames, 2021; Elwell et al., 2016; Renvoisé et al., 2011; van Schaik et al., 2013), the interactions and effects on the hosts are still poorly characterized.

Holosporales are another diversified lineage of professional symbionts (Husnik et al., 2021; Szokoli et al., 2016). Just like the *Rickettsiales*, they belong to the *Alphaproteobacteria*, but with a distinct phylogenetic branching (Muñoz-Gómez et al., 2019). Accordingly, it is implied that the evolution from free-living alphaproteobacterial ancestors to obligate host-associated professional symbionts has occurred independently (and convergently) for the two lineages. Therefore, *Holosporales* together with *Rickettsiales* make an ideal ground for evolutionary comparisons on the emergence and diversification of professional symbionts.

Holosporales are comparatively under-explored, in particular, few genome sequences are currently available, also due to the lack of relevant human pathogens, while a shrimp pathogen is known (Nunan et al., 2013). Nevertheless, *Holosporales* include noteworthy representatives, such as the infectious intranuclear *Holospira*, *Holospira*-like bacteria (Beliavskaia et al., 2020; Schrollhammer & Potekhin, 2020; Zilio et al., 2021), and ‘*Candidatus Nucleicultrix*’ (Schulz et al., 2014) (from now on, *Candidatus* will be abbreviated as *Ca.*), or ‘*Caedimonas*’, which confers to its host a killer-trait towards non-infected conspecifics involving the peculiar proteinaceous R-bodies (Schrollhammer et al., 2018). R-bodies were also found in a number of phylogenetically unrelated non-*Holosporales* bacteria, with potential involvement in host interactions (Raymann et al., 2013; Schrollhammer & Schweikert, 2009; Wang et al., 2021),

but, to our knowledge, until now never described in other *Holosporales*.

Three *Holosporales* families, namely *Holosporaceae*, ‘*Caedimonadaceae*’ and ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’, form a monophylum (Muñoz-Gómez et al., 2019; Szokoli et al., 2016). *Holosporaceae* are intracellularly associated with protists, such as ciliates and diplomonads (Boscaro et al., 2019; Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022; George et al., 2020; Korotaev et al., 2020; Potekhin et al., 2021; Shiohama et al., 2022; Szokoli et al., 2016; Tashyreva et al., 2018), as well as with arthropods, such as crustaceans and arachnids (Konecka & Olszanowski, 2019; Nunan et al., 2013). According to the available genome sequences, a trend towards genome reduction was evidenced within this family, reaching much more extreme levels than other *Holosporales* and in general other professional symbionts (frequently below 1 Mb, down to ~600 Kb) (Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022; George et al., 2020; Shiohama et al., 2022). The most streamlined *Holosporaceae* genomes are almost devoid of repeated elements, but retain a set of DNA recombination and repair systems. While in some cases potential parasitic effects were suggested (Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022), the role of most *Holosporaceae* for their hosts was not clarified.

‘*Caedimonadaceae*’ and ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’ are typically intracellularly hosted by multiple protists as well, such as amoebas, ciliates and cercozoans (Boscaro et al., 2019; Georgiades et al., 2011; Hess et al., 2016; Horn et al., 1999; Schrollhammer et al., 2018). They display relatively large genomes for obligatorily host-associated bacteria (up to 2.84 Mb) (Wang & Wu, 2015), hinting at relatively complex interactions and/or more recent adaptations. A fourth *Holosporales* lineage is composed of the family ‘*Ca. Hepatincolaceae*’ (Szokoli et al., 2016) (also named ‘*Ca. Tenuibacteraceae*’ [Kroer et al., 2016]). Its representatives were extracellularly found in the gut of arthropods and other ecdysozoans (Dittmer et al., 2023; Guidetti et al., 2020; Kroer et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2004), which possibly represents an ancestral or divergent condition.

The phylogenetic position of *Holosporales* makes them an ideal ground for evolutionary comparisons on the emergence and diversification of professional symbionts. Indeed, just like the *Rickettsiales*, they belong to the *Alphaproteobacteria*, thus representing a case of convergently evolved lifestyles within the same class (Muñoz-Gómez et al., 2019).

In this work, we aimed to investigate the genome evolutionary trends among *Holosporaceae* and *Holosporales*. For this purpose, we selected ‘*Ca. Bealeia paramacronuclearis*’ (from now on, *Bealeia paramacronuclearis*), a representative of the *Holosporaceae* (Szokoli et al., 2016) which is distinctive for its peculiar

early-diverging phylogenetic positioning within this family, and for which until now no genome sequence is available. Thus, we started with de novo sequencing of two *Bealeia paramacronuclearis* associated with two different strains of the ciliate *Paramecium biaurelia* (Szokoli et al., 2016). The newly sequenced genomes are to our knowledge the largest among *Holosporaceae* (~1.8 Mbp), akin to representatives of other *Holosporales* families. Accordingly, novel insight into recent and convergent genome reduction within *Holosporales* was obtained, partly reminiscent of those patterns previously identified among the *Rickettsiales* (Castelli, Nardi, et al., 2022).

RESULTS

General genome features of the *Bealeia* endosymbionts

A complete circular chromosome assembly (1,855,636 bp; GC = 42.7%) was generated for *Bealeia* strain US_BI 1511, while a 4-contigs assembly was obtained for strain US_BI 11111 (1,823,554 bp; N50 = 934,875 bp; L50 = 1; GC = 42.8%) (Table 1; Supplementary Figure 1). To the best of our knowledge, these are the largest reported genomes in the family *Holosporaceae* (Supplementary Figure 2). The Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI) was 99.96% between US_BI 11111 and US_BI 1511, indicating that both strains belong to the same species (threshold 95%: [Goris et al., 2007]) and are very closely related, in agreement with the 100% identity of the respective SSU rRNA gene sequences (Szokoli et al., 2016). Moreover, a total of 6 plasmidic contigs (including 5 circular plasmids) and 13 plasmidic contigs (including 6 circular plasmids) were obtained for US_BI 1511 and US_BI

11111, respectively (Supplementary Figure 3). The completeness of the two full assemblies (chromosome + plasmids) was further confirmed by the analysis of conserved orthologs in *Proteobacteria* with BUSCO v3 (Simão et al., 2015), showing even higher levels with respect to other *Holosporaceae* (Supplementary Figure 4).

Comparisons between the two *Bealeia* genomes

The Mummer analysis indicated a highly conserved synteny between the two *Bealeia* chromosomal genomes (Supplementary Figure 5). Moreover, only two genomic segments larger than 1000 bp (~14,498 bp and ~25,977 bp) were observed US_BI 1511 and not in US_BI 11111, and none vice versa.

Orthogroup comparison showed that the two strains share almost all genome content, namely 98.9% of 2112 total combined Clusters of Orthologous Genes (COGs) shared. In detail, only 10 COGs were specific for strain US_BI 1511 and 14 for strain US_BI 11111 (Supplementary Table 1). Noteworthy among the US_BI 1511-specific COGs is a predicted protein-encoding tetratricopeptide repeat (TPR), potentially involved in protein–protein complexes, including those exerting roles in symbiont–host interactions (Castelli, Nardi, et al., 2022; Schulz et al., 2016). Almost all peculiar COGs of *Bealeia* US_BI 11111 are plasmid-encoded, and their predicted functions are overall unclear, being derived from generic predictions and/or not confirmed by direct sequence comparison. The single chromosome-encoded COG specific to this strain is an RTX family protein, which may be involved in host interactions (Benz, 2016).

Therefore, considering the high sequence identity and the almost identical functional content from COGs, only the US_BI 1511 strain was used as representative for the subsequent analyses, unless otherwise stated.

TABLE 1 Summary of features of the two *Bealeia paramacronuclearis* assembled genomes.

	'Ca. <i>Bealeia paramacronuclearis</i> ' US_BI 1511	'Ca. <i>Bealeia paramacronuclearis</i> ' US_BI 11111
Host species	<i>Paramecium biaurelia</i> US_BI 1511	<i>Paramecium biaurelia</i> US_BI 11111
Sequencing method	Illumina + Nanopore	Illumina + Nanopore
Assembly level	Complete	Scaffold
No. of contigs	1 (circular)	4 (linear)
Length (bp)	1,855,636	1,823,554
GC content (%)	42.7	42.8
Total genes	1939	1886
No. of plasmids	6 (5 closed circularly)	13 (6 closed circularly)

Phylogenomic analyses confirmed the affiliation of *Bealeia* to *Holosporaceae*

The phylogenomic results confirmed the overall topology of the 16S rRNA gene phylogeny (Szokoli et al., 2016), providing more robust statistical support. In detail, in the 'full organism dataset' ML and BI analyses produced identical topology (Figure 1), placing the *Holosporaceae* family as the sister group of the 'Caedimonadaceae' (81 ML | 1.00 BI), with the 'Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae' as early-diverging lineage within the order *Holosporales*. As expected, *Bealeia paramacronuclearis* was assigned to the *Holosporaceae* (65 ML | 1.00 BI), specifically in the earliest-diverging position among the representatives of this

~50% richer than the second ranked 'Ca. Hepatobacter', and roughly doubling all others) (Figure 2A). On the other hand, in terms of total numbers, and by functional categories, it is, in general, similar to members of the other *Holosporales* families, including the closely-related 'Caedimonadaceae' (Suzuki et al., 2015; Wang & Wu, 2015). This is not surprising, as *Bealeia* is early-diverging in the *Holosporaceae* family, and is its relatively slowest-evolving representative, as opposed to the fast-evolving *Holosporaceae*, characterized by strongly reduced genomes (Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022; George et al., 2020). Overall, variations in COG numbers are proportional to the respective genome sizes among

Holosporales ($R^2 = 0.8669$, F-statistic p-value = $1.262e^{-08}$; Supplementary Figure 2). This association underscores the strong influence of genome size on the functional repertoire of *Holosporales*, which could have implications for their adaptive strategies with their hosts.

We performed a general analysis of gene content variation (based on COGs) across the *Holosporales* with phylogenetic birth-and-death models. Accordingly, we observed that consistently with the expectations for host-associated bacteria, gene loss was highly prevalent, with the ancestor of all *Holosporales* showing the largest gene content (Supplementary Figure 7; Supplementary Table 2).

FIGURE 2 Comparisons of the cluster of orthology group (COG) functional repertoire of *Bealeia* with other *Holosporales*. (A) Barplots representing each bacterium and the numbers of COGs assigned to each category. For viewers' clarity, categories were merged into loosely related groups. Bacteria are ordered by the phylogenetic branching in Figure 1, with *Bealeia* highlighted by an asterisk. (B) Venn diagram comparison of *Bealeia* total COG repertoire with the other *Holosporaceae* arranged in four groups according to their phylogenetic proximity. (C) Venn diagram comparison of *Bealeia* total COG repertoire with the members of each of three *Holosporales* families ('Caedimonadaceae', 'Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae' and other *Holosporaceae*).

We then performed direct comparisons of the functional genome contents across the *Holosporales*. To this purpose, the representatives of the family *Holosporaceae* other than *Bealeia* were combined into four functionally homogeneous and evolutionarily-consistent groups, based on phylogeny (Figure 1) and previous comparative genomic studies (Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022; Garushyants et al., 2018; George et al., 2020). Specifically, the members of the monophyletic ‘fastest-evolving’ *Holosporaceae* genera, namely ‘*Ca. Cytomitobacter*’, ‘*Ca. Nesciobacter*’ and ‘*Ca. Gromoviella*’, were combined, as well as those of each of the other three genera (*Holospira*, ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’, ‘*Ca. Hydrogenosomobacter*’). In total, 355 COGs are shared among *Bealeia* and all the four other groups (Figure 2B). Consistent with the higher total COG numbers (Figure 2A), *Bealeia* is distinctive because it contains the markedly highest number of unique COGs among the *Holosporaceae* (282). Conversely, other 318 COGs were retrieved in at least another *Holosporaceae* representative, and not in *Bealeia*. While ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’ is the richest in COGs besides *Bealeia* (Figure 2B), most of those ‘non-*Bealeia*’ COGs (165/318) are specific to the *Holospira* spp. (Figure 2B).

When extending the comparison to the other families of *Holosporales*, only 54 out of the 282 *Bealeia*-specific COGs among *Holosporaceae* are still unique to this bacterium, while the other 228 are shared with at least one member of ‘*Caedimonadaceae*’ and/or ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’ (Figure 2C). Moreover, 562 additional COGs are present in some member of those two families and absent in *Bealeia* (Figure 2C).

Below, a detailed comparison of the predicted metabolic and functional repertoire of *Bealeia* with the four other groups of *Holosporaceae* will follow, as well as with the ‘*Caedimonadaceae*’ and ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’ families.

Carbohydrate and energetic metabolism

In terms of carbohydrate and energetic metabolism, *Bealeia* is rather richer than other *Holosporaceae* (Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022; Garushyants et al., 2018; George et al., 2020; Wang & Wu, 2015). In detail, enzymes necessary for complete glycolysis and gluconeogenesis are present in *Bealeia*. This is a striking difference with respect to the other members of the family, which are almost completely devoid of those. The few exceptions are the initial steps of gluconeogenesis in just two bacteria (up to phosphoenolpyruvate in ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’, and to pyruvate in the fastest-evolving ‘*Ca. Gromoviella*’), and few widespread genes such as the triose and glucose-phosphate isomerases. The non-oxidative branch of the pentose-phosphate pathway is present in *Bealeia*

as well, similar to ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’ and *Holospira* spp., while it is only partial in the other *Holosporaceae*.

Moreover, the *Bealeia* genome encodes all genes of the tricarboxylic acid cycle (TCA), while this pathway is partial (only from 2-oxoglutarate) in ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’, and absent in all other *Holosporaceae*. In parallel, all electron transport complexes (including cytochrome c reductase and oxidase, and the alternative bd ubiquinol terminal oxidase) are present in *Bealeia*, while ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’ retains only a minimal set of complexes I, II, and the bd oxidase, and other *Holosporaceae* have none of those. Conversely, pyruvate dehydrogenase and ATP synthase are shared among all *Holosporaceae*, including *Bealeia*. The presence of the pyruvate dehydrogenase can be explained by considering that the resulting acetyl-CoA is not required only by TCA, but also for biosynthetic pathways, chiefly for (phospho)lipids (Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022). Moreover, *Bealeia* and ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’ display the enzyme repertoire to employ acetyl-CoA for the synthesis of the storage compounds polyhydroxyalkanoate (PHA) granules, similar to many *Rickettsiales* (Castelli et al., 2021; Driscoll et al., 2017; Sabaneyeva et al., 2018; Schulz et al., 2016).

Thus, *Bealeia* is the only known *Holosporaceae* able to derive energy directly from hexose sugars, and the only one (besides ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’) able to produce ATP from catabolic processes. It also displays an equivalent or higher ability of sugar metabolism than its relatives, possibly for biosynthetic purposes (see below). On the other hand, we found the *Bealeia* repertoire for all such described metabolic pathways as consistent with representatives of ‘*Caedimonadaceae*’ and ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’.

Amino acid and nucleotide metabolism

Biosynthetic abilities for metabolic precursors and cofactors of *Bealeia* are, as in other *Holosporales*, very scarce. Regarding amino acids, as common in *Holosporales*, *Bealeia* can obtain alanine via cysteine desulfurase. Moreover, as a unique case among *Holosporaceae*, but similar to members of the other families, it possesses a glutamine synthetase, as well as the enzyme for the last step of proline biosynthesis (i.e., starting from pyrroline-5-carboxylate), the latter possibly representing the result of an ancestral reduction of the pathway among *Holosporales*. *Bealeia* can obtain glutamine from glutamate, just like members of the other families and *Holospira* spp. among *Holosporaceae*. Conversely, all *Holosporales* including *Bealeia* can obtain glycine from serine, except the *Holospira* genus and ‘*Ca. Hydrogenosomobacter*’. Despite being able to produce diamminopimelate (employed for peptidoglycan synthesis, see below), *Bealeia* is unable to synthesize lysine, similarly to all other *Holosporales*

except the ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’ bacterium ‘*Ca. Finniella*’, which also presents the lysine-producing diaminopimelate decarboxylase. Finally, a distinctive trait of *Bealeia* among all *Holosporales* is the presence of an O-acetylhomoserine aminocarboxypropyltransferase/cysteine synthase gene, which may enable the synthesis of cysteine (Ferla & Patrick, 2014). In sum, amino acid biosynthetic abilities of *Bealeia* are limited, and, while overall comparable to the other *Holosporales* families, still more abundant than in the other *Holosporaceae*, which have at most a subset of its pathways. The only partial exception is ‘*Holospira curviuscula*’, which presents the genes for tryptophan synthesis from anthranilate organized in a single operon. The predicted proteins have high identities with host-associated bacteria other than *Holosporales* (Supplementary Table 3) and are therefore attributable to putative horizontal gene transfer (HGT) events.

Bealeia lacks the capacity for de novo nucleotide biosynthesis, with some partial exceptions. Namely, similarly to the members of the other two *Holosporales* families, as well as to ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’, ‘*Ca. Nesciobacter*’ and ‘*Ca. Cytomitobacter spp.*’, it can produce deoxythymidine from uracil. It is also able to produce CTP from UTP thanks to the *pyrG* gene, a trait shared with the other *Holosporales* and *Holosporaceae* besides ‘*Ca. Gromoviella*’.

Similarly to all *Holosporales* with few exceptions, *Bealeia* displays nucleotide recycling and interconversion abilities. Specifically, it possesses adenylate, uridylylate and guanylate kinases (the latter absent in the fastest-evolving *Holosporaceae*), and nucleoside diphosphate kinase (*ndk*). It is also able to convert ribonucleosides into the corresponding deoxyribonucleosides, as other *Holosporales* except ‘*Ca. Hydrogenosomobacter*’, ‘*Ca. Nesciobacter*’ and ‘*Ca. Cytomitobacter spp.*’.

Accordingly, *Bealeia*, similarly to other *Holosporales*, likely relies on the uptake from its host of most amino acids and some nucleotides (at least ribonucleic adenosine, uridine and guanosine). Among potential transporters notable is a NupC nucleoside permease, sharing homologues in ‘*Ca. Hydrogenosomobacter*’, as well as among ‘*Caedimonadaceae*’ and ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’. Moreover, two *tlc* nucleotide translocase genes were also identified in *Bealeia*. Homologues of those are known in all previously sequenced *Holosporales* genomes (Garushyants et al., 2018; George et al., 2020) and in many other obligate intracellular bacteria (Major et al., 2017; Schmitz-Esser et al., 2004). In addition to energy supply, the proteins were recently hypothesized to be involved also in the provision of nucleic acids metabolic precursors among the *Rickettsiales* (Castelli, Nardi, et al., 2022). Our phylogenetic analyses indicate that *Tlc* translocases are non-monophyletic in *Holosporales* in general, and specifically in the *Holosporaceae* family (Supplementary Figure 8). In particular, the two *Bealeia*

sequences are not closely related, nor are the two other *Paramecium* symbiont ‘*Ca. Gromoviella*’. On the other hand, those of the diplomid symbionts ‘*Ca. Cytomitobacter*’ and ‘*Ca. Nesciobacter*’ form a highly supported monophyletic group, with three subgroups containing one sequence per organism, with relationships consistent with organismal phylogeny (Figure 1).

Metabolism of biotin and other cofactors

Regarding coenzyme and cofactor biosynthetic capabilities, *Bealeia* lies at an intermediate level between other *Holosporaceae* and members of the other families. Just like the latter, it can produce heme and ubiquinone, while within *Holosporaceae* only ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’ is equivalent, and in addition, *Holospira spp.* can synthesize ubiquinone but not heme. This is consistent with the presence/absence patterns among *Holosporales* of electron transport complexes that include heme or ubiquinone as prosthetic groups (Aussel et al., 2014; Borisov et al., 2011; Yankovskaya et al., 2003), except for *Holospira*, in which ubiquinone may be involved in other functions (Aussel et al., 2014). In addition, the *Bealeia* genome encodes for the lipoate biosynthetic pathway, similarly to other *Holosporales*, with the only exception of the fast-evolving ‘*Ca. Cytomitobacter spp.*’. Like *Holospira spp.* and ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’, *Bealeia* is also able to produce NADP(H) from NAD(H) by a NAD kinase.

Similarly to the other *Holosporaceae*, and differently from members ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’ and/or ‘*Caedimonadaceae*’, *Bealeia* is fully unable to synthesize CoA, riboflavin, folate or NAD.

On the other hand, *Bealeia* is more defective than some other *Holosporaceae* in a couple of pathways. Specifically, differently from ‘*Ca. Hydrogenosomobacter*’ and ‘*Caedimonas*’ among ‘*Caedimonadaceae*’ it is unable to produce thiamine.

Moreover, while *Holospira spp.* can synthesize biotin, *Bealeia* is not, just like all other *Holosporaceae*. However, *Bealeia* has the *bioY* gene for a biotin transporter, which may enable it to import this vitamin from the host, and this gene is found also in ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’. Interestingly, this inverse correlation between the presence of biotin biosynthesis and transport is maintained also in other *Holosporales*, with relevant variations within each family. Namely, ‘*Caedimonadaceae*’ are unable to synthesize this compound, but are mostly equipped with the transporter (except ‘*Ca. Nucleicultrix*’), while ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’ are competent in the biosynthesis and devoid of the transporter (except ‘*Ca. Finniella*’, which possesses the transporter and lacks the pathway). Phylogenetic relationships of the biotin biosynthetic enzymes retrieved all the involved *Holosporales* from different families as monophyletic with full support (Figure 3A;

FIGURE 3 Phylogenetic analyses on biotin synthesis and transport. (A) Phylogenetic tree of the concatenated biotin synthesis genes in *Holosporales* and other *Alphaproteobacteria*. Members of each *Holosporales* family are evidenced by different colours. On each branch, support values by SH-aLRT with 1000 replicates and by 1000 ultrafast bootstraps are reported. The tree scale stands for estimated proportional sequence divergence. For visualization purposes, outgroup sequences and large alphaproteobacterial clades not including *Holosporales* sequences are collapsed and represented as triangular shapes. The full tree is shown in Supplementary Figure 9. (B) Phylogenetic tree of the BioY biotin transporters. Sequences and leading branches of a member of each *Holosporales* family are evidenced by different colours. The newly obtained sequence of *Bealeia* is highlighted in bold. The tree scale stands for estimated proportional sequence divergence. The full tree including support values is shown in Supplementary Figure 10.

Supplementary Figure 9), and with reciprocal relationships, including in particular the grouping of families, consistent with organismal phylogenies (Figure 1). On

the other hand, the BioY transporters of *Holosporales* are mostly phylogenetically unrelated to each other, with the only potential exception of the two

Holosporaceae Bealeia and ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’, being sister groups, but with only partial support (Figure 3B; Supplementary Figure 10).

Cell membrane and wall

The capabilities to synthesize the main components of the cell membrane and wall in *Bealeia* are overall consistent with other *Holosporales* and other *Alphaproteobacteria* (Castelli et al., 2019, 2021; Floriano et al., 2018; Garushyants et al., 2018). Produced components include fatty acids from acetyl-CoA and phospholipids from putatively host-derived dihydroxyacetone phosphate, thanks to an NADPH-dependent glycerol-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (this enzyme is absent in ‘*Ca. Gromoviella*’). Peptidoglycan can also be synthesized by *Bealeia* starting from fructose 6-phosphate, but only some of the other precursors involved can be autonomously synthesized, for example, D-alanine from L-alanine (thanks to two alanine racemases) and diaminopimelate from aspartate, the latter trait shared with other *Holosporales* except ‘*Ca. Gromoviella*’ among the fast-evolving *Holosporaceae*.

At the same time, like *Holospira* spp., ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’, ‘*Ca. Hydrogenosomobacter*’, and members of the other *Holosporales* families, *Bealeia* is also equipped with the capabilities to synthesize lipopolysaccharide (LPS). Conversely, the lack of such genes in the fastest-evolving *Holosporaceae* (Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022; George et al., 2020) suggests a different cell envelope structure in these organisms, possibly representing an adaptation to close host-associated lifestyles, as LPS may elicit immune responses in some eukaryotic hosts (Bennett et al., 2014; Lin & Rikihisa, 2003).

While the methylerythritol phosphate pathway is common in ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’, *Bealeia* and other members of the monophylum including *Holosporaceae* and ‘*Caedimonadaceae*’ are unable to synthesize autonomously isoprenoid precursors.

Protein secretion, adhesion, motility

Bealeia displays several systems for protein secretion, possibly involved in the interaction with the *Paramecium* host. This set is overall consistent with other *Holosporales* (George et al., 2020). Specifically, Sec translocon is present, as in all other *Holosporales* besides the fastest-evolving *Holosporaceae*, among which the only set is the co-translational transport in ‘*Ca. Gromoviella*’ (Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022). As common in *Holosporales*, *Bealeia* is equipped with additional systems helping to translocate proteins to the outer membrane (Lol) or transport them outside the cell (Bam). It also possesses the Sec-independent Tat system, a quite rare condition among *Holosporaceae*

and *Holosporales* in general, being shared only with ‘*Ca. Gromoviella*’, ‘*Caedimonas*’ and ‘*Ca. Finniella*’.

Furthermore, as typical in almost all *Holosporales* (Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022; George et al., 2020), with the exceptions of *Holospira* spp. and ‘*Ca. Hydrogenosomobacter*’, *Bealeia* has a modified type VI secretion system (T6SS). As several other *Holosporales* belonging to each of the three families (Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022; George et al., 2020), *Bealeia* also presents the components of a type II secretion/type IV pilus, namely ATPase, inner- and outer membrane complexes, and a pseudopilin.

Similarly to many ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’ and ‘*Ca. Nucleicultrix*’ among ‘*Caedimonadaceae*’, *Bealeia* is equipped with a putative complete flagellar apparatus, including flagellin. Conversely, among other *Holosporaceae*, ‘*Ca. Hepatobacter*’ possesses only a partial set (Leyva et al., 2017), devoid of filament and hook, and other members fully lack this organelle. Besides, we identified a gene set for chemotaxis in *Bealeia*, unique among *Holosporaceae*, as well as in the ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’ bacterium ‘*Ca. Odysella*’.

Bealeia presents the components of the Flp/Tad pilus, which could be found also in representatives of each of the other two *Holosporales* families, but not in other *Holosporaceae*. Moreover, *Bealeia* can synthesize poly-β-1,6-*N*-acetyl-D-glucosamine and deacetylate it (a function involved in its export), while other *Holosporaceae* and *Holosporales* are unable to. In other bacteria, this process is involved in the formation of biofilm (Little et al., 2014), potentially active in some extracellular stages of *Bealeia*, for example, during horizontal transmission. Interestingly, the deacetylase gene is complete only in US_BI 11III1, while in US_BI 15I1 it is interrupted (and possibly functionally impaired) by a transposase gene close to its 3’ end.

The *Bealeia* genome encodes also for (potentially secreted) proteins bearing domains associated with protein–protein interactions and considered important in symbiont–host interactions (Castelli, Nardi, et al., 2022; Schulz et al., 2016), namely nine tetratricopeptide repeats-containing proteins, four leucine-rich repeats-containing proteins, and 4 RTX toxins (two in US_BI 15I1, one plasmidic more in US_BI 11III1; see above), the latter sharing a single homologue in ‘*Caedimonas*’ among all *Holosporales*.

R-body determinants

While inspecting the genes encoded in the *Bealeia* plasmids, some ORFs were found with homology to the *reb* genes, namely the determinants of R-bodies in the *Paramecium* symbiont *Caedibacter taeniospiralis* (Schrallhammer & Schweikert, 2009) and in other bacteria (Wang et al., 2021). This finding was unexpected, as no R-bodies were observed in ultrastructural

investigations on *Bealeia* (Szokoli et al., 2016). We thus aimed to get a comprehensive overview of the presence of *reb* genes in *Bealeia* and in other *Holosporales* in general. We identified several Reb homologues in both *Bealeia* strains, namely six genes organized in a putative operon in the largest plasmid of

US_BI 1511, and 10 genes in US_BI 11111, of which six organized in a putative plasmidic operon similarly to US_BI 1511, and four others representing a putative partially duplicated operon on other plasmids (Figure 4). Moreover, confirming previous investigations (Suzuki et al., 2015) eight homologues were found

FIGURE 4 Analyses on the Reb homologues, putative determinants of R-bodies, in *Holosporales* and other bacteria. (A) Phylogenetic tree of the Reb homologues. Sequences and leading branches of a member of each *Holosporales* family and the gammaproteobacterium *Caedibacter taeniospiralis* are evidenced by different colours, and the two RebA/B and RebD clusters of those organisms are highlighted in blue and purple, respectively. The scale bar stands for estimated proportional sequence divergence. The full tree including support values is shown in Supplementary Figure 11. (B) Scheme of the genomic location of *reb* genes, including putative operons, in *Holosporales* (enclosed in a dashed-line rectangular box) and, for comparison, *C. taeniospiralis*. Each line stands for a distinct assembled contig, and each arrow indicates the direction of the respective gene. RebD and RebA/B of *C. taeniospiralis* and their phylogenetically closest *Holosporales* homologues are highlighted in blue and purple, respectively. Homologues with high identity ($\geq 98.3\%$) between the two *Bealeia* strains are connected by grey shapes. Genes are labelled according to their locus tag (*Bealeia*) or protein accession number (other organisms).

in the R-body producer ‘*Caedimonas varicaedens*’, of which four and three, respectively, organized in two putative operons. Finally, three genes were found organized in a putative operon in the ‘*Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae*’ bacterium ‘*Ca. Finniella inopinata*’, which is not known for producing R-bodies (Hess et al., 2016). The fragmented status of the latter two assemblies did not allow for the assignment of the respective contigs to bacterial chromosomes or plasmids, although for ‘*Caedimonas varicaedens*’ an extrachromosomal location was previously suggested (Schrallhammer et al., 2005). Phylogenetic analyses indicated that the Reb proteins of *Holosporales* are closely related, being clustered in two groups, each with at least one representative per organism (Figure 4; Supplementary Figure 11). The major group, related to RebA/B of the gammaproteobacterial symbiont *C. taeniospiralis*, includes a monophyletic assemblage of *Holosporales* sequences, within which sequences from the same organism are only partially clustered together. The second group, together with *Holosporales*, also includes the RebD sequence from *C. taeniospiralis*, which resulted closely related to some *Bealeia* and ‘*Caedimonas*’ sequences, as well as two sequences from the alphaproteobacterium *Brevundimonas*.

Within both groups, each US_BI 1511 sequence was found in a close relationship with one or two US_BI 11111 counterparts, consistently with the respective high amino acid identities ($\geq 98\%$) and with the putative presence of the complete and partial homologous operons hypothesized above.

Additional genome features

Consistently with the high fragmentation (and contig connection degree) of the short-reads assembly (Supplementary Text 1), multiple repeat elements were found in the *Bealeia* genome, including 330 ORFs showing homology to transposases, and seven to phage genes. In terms of DNA repair abilities, *Bealeia* is equipped with nucleotide excision repair, mismatch repair, RecFOR, and single-strand break repair, including RuvABC resolvase. This is consistent with most *Holosporaceae* (besides the fastest-evolving, lacking nucleotide excision repair and single-strand break repair, except for the RecFOR in ‘*Ca. Gromoviella*’) and *Holosporales*. A plasmid-encoded protelomerase was identified. Interestingly, this enzyme is involved in replication of linear bacterial plasmids (Kobryn & Chaconas, 2002; Shi et al., 2013).

DISCUSSION

In this work, thanks to hybrid Illumina and Nanopore assembly, we newly obtained the high-quality genome

assemblies of two *B. paramacronuclearis* (*Holosporaceae*) endosymbionts of the ciliate *P. biaurelia* strains US_BI 1511 and US_BI 11111, respectively (Szokoli et al., 2016). Each assembly included a chromosome and multiple plasmids. Here, the novel sequences represented the basis for extensive comparative genomic analyses, allowing us to get novel insights on general evolutionary trends for the whole *Holosporales*.

Until now, due to the paucity of available genomic sequences, most phylogenetic studies on *Holosporales* relied only on 16S rRNA gene sequences (Konecka & Olszanowski, 2019; Korotaev et al., 2020; Szokoli et al., 2016; Takeshita et al., 2019; Tashyreva et al., 2018), which however could not resolve with high support multiple inner relationships. Here, the newly obtained *Bealeia* genome allowed us to get much more reliable reconstructions. Specifically, this bacterium was placed in an early-divergent and shorter branch within the *Holosporaceae*, which was retrieved in a sister-group relationship with ‘*Caedimonadaceae*’ with high supports (Figure 1). Interestingly, such tree topologies are consistent with the lowly supported 16S rRNA gene phylogeny (Szokoli et al., 2016), thereby confirming at least in this case its predictive power. Moreover, even as compared to previous *Holosporales* phylogenomics (Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022; George et al., 2020), the improved support for the positioning of *Holosporaceae* indicates that the inclusion of *Bealeia* allowed to eventually stabilize their positioning in phylogenetic reconstructions. Such a stabilized inference of the phylogenetic relationships between *Holosporales* represented the necessary basis for the successive evolutionary analyses on predicted functions.

In general, *Bealeia* genomes present typical features of obligate intracellular bacteria and specifically professional symbionts (Bennett & Moran, 2015; Gillespie et al., 2014; Husnik et al., 2021; Moran et al., 2008; Renvoisé et al., 2011), such as genome reduction, indicative of deep metabolic dependence on their hosts, and a set of secretion systems (in particular type VI and type II), putatively involved in the release of effectors to modulate interactions with the host.

Consistent with the earlier and shorter branching, *Bealeia* presents an overall less pronounced genome reduction than other *Holosporaceae*, being more akin to members of the other *Holosporales* families (Figure 2), although several lineage-specific peculiarities were identified, as detailed in the Results). *Bealeia*-specific traits among *Holosporaceae* pertain to multiple functions, ranging from carbohydrate and energy metabolism (glycolysis, gluconeogenesis, TCA cycle, and oxidative phosphorylation), to motility (complete set of flagellar and chemotaxis genes, including flagellin). Regarding flagellar genes, their actual function is not clear, since no flagella have been observed in *Bealeia* (Szokoli et al., 2016), nor in several other *Holosporales* equipped with flagellar genes (Birtles

et al., 2000; Horn et al., 1999; Schulz et al., 2014). Multiple non-exclusive explanations can be considered. First, flagella might be present, but not have been detected due to insufficient sensitivity of the methods used for electron microscopy (Sabaneyeva et al., 2018). Alternatively, it could be that flagellar gene expression is conditional, and triggered by conditions different from those experienced in the previously examined laboratory settings (Castelli, Nardi, et al., 2022). Specifically, as proposed for other symbionts, in *Bealeia* and other *Holosporales*, flagella may be involved in extracellular motility during horizontal transmission (Collingro et al., 2017; Sasser et al., 2010; Schulz et al., 2016), adhesion to/invasion of host cells (Floriano et al., 2022; Siewert et al., 2022), or even in delivery of effector molecules, due to their type III secretion component (Abby & Rocha, 2012). Further experimental analyses will be necessary to elucidate this.

Relevant evolutionary patterns were found for the metabolism of nucleotides and biotin in *Holosporales*. Regarding nucleotides, *Holosporales* are unable of de novo synthesis and are equipped with transporters for their uptake, such as Tlc translocases and NupC permeases. Phylogeny of transporters indicates more than a single HGT acquisition in the *Holosporales* (Supplementary Figure 8), followed by multiple independent lineage-specific duplications, in particular among the fastest-evolving *Holosporales*. This reconstruction is partly reminiscent of the *Rickettsiales*, however in that case the pattern of presence of either transporters or biosynthetic genes is more ‘patchy’ along the organismal phylogeny (Castelli, Nardi, et al., 2022). This could be tentatively related to the more ‘uniform’ localization of the investigated *Holosporales*, typically residing intracellularly without surrounding vacuoles that may limit the availability of the host’s nucleotides. This can be confronted with the more diverse *Rickettsiales*, which include intracellular naked or vacuole-dwelling representatives (Renvoisé et al., 2011), as well as extracellular ones (Castelli et al., 2019) (and possibly even non-host associated others [Schön et al., 2022]). The case of biotin seems even more distinctive, showing a ‘patchy’ alternative distribution of synthesis and transport in *Holosporales*, highly comparable to the nucleotides (and amino acids) in the *Rickettsiales*. Specifically, most *Holosporales*, including *Bealeia*, are fully devoid of the biosynthetic pathway, except for some representatives of two relatively distant families (*Holosporaceae* and ‘Ca. Paracaedibacteraceae’). The respective biosynthesis genes are monophyletic and consistent with organismal phylogeny (Figure 3A), also showing phylogenetic proximity to some *Rhodospirillales* (which include the closest relatives of *Holosporales* [Muñoz-Gómez et al., 2019]). On the other hand, BioY biotin transporters of the *Holosporales*, present in *Bealeia*

and representatives of each family lacking the biosynthesis, resulted as non-monophyletic (Figure 3B).

Taken together, those data suggest a scenario in which multiple features involved in host interaction and host dependence would have emerged multiple times independently among the *Holosporales*. Such a general trend seems at least partly comparable to previous inferences on the *Rickettsiales* (Castelli et al., 2019; Castelli, Nardi, et al., 2022), in particular concerning the effect of multiple independent acquisition of transporters, leading to a progressive convergent loss of ancestral biosynthetic pathways in the different sublineages and thus driving evolution of host-dependence and genome reduction (Supplementary Figure 12). Nevertheless, some significant differences could be also delineated. For instance, putatively analogous but distinct molecular machinery is involved, in particular, the presence of a type VI secretion system in *Holosporales* (George et al., 2020) as compared to the type IV secretion typical in *Rickettsiales* (Gillespie et al., 2010, 2014). Moreover, *Holosporales* genome features appear overall more uniform than *Rickettsiales*, which might be related to their more recent origin and diversification, according to the branching pattern within *Alphaproteobacteria* (Castelli, Nardi, et al., 2022; Muñoz-Gómez et al., 2019). At the same time, some *Holosporales* may reach seemingly extreme conditions, such as the highly pronounced genome reduction among the fast-evolving *Holosporaceae* (Castelli, Lanzoni, et al., 2022; George et al., 2020), or the peculiar infectious life cycles of *Holospora* (Schrallhammer & Potekhin, 2020) and ‘Ca. Nucleicultrix’ (Schulz et al., 2014).

From this perspective, the *reb* genes, putatively encoding for the R-bodies, are distinctive. R-bodies are proteinaceous structures well known for being involved in the competitively advantageous killer trait conferred to *Paramecium* by *Caedibacter* or by the *Holosporales* bacterium ‘*Caedimonas*’ towards non-infected conspecifics (Schrallhammer & Schweikert, 2009), and likely modulating interactions with eukaryotes in several other bacteria (Wang et al., 2021). Herein, we found *reb* genes also in *Bealeia* and in ‘Ca. Finniella inopinata’ (thus, collectively in one species for each of the three *Holosporales* families), suggesting that these bacteria are competent for R-bodies production, despite these were never observed (Hess et al., 2016; Szokoli et al., 2016). Unlike flagella, R-bodies are quite distinct in electron microscopy investigations (Schrallhammer & Schweikert, 2009), but could still have remained unnoticed due to low abundance, or they may not have been expressed in the examined laboratory conditions. Reb proteins of *Holosporales* belong to two phylogenetic clusters, with branching patterns comparable to the organismal phylogeny (Figure 4). Considering that Reb proteins are typically plasmid-encoded, it seems not unlikely that this

FIGURE 5 Legend on next page.

condition could have resulted from multiple HGT events (Figure 5). On the other hand, it is noteworthy that *reb* genes are quite frequent in *Holospirales*, but never found in other more deeply investigated lineages of professional symbionts (*Rickettsiales*, *Legionellales*, *Chlamydiae*). Assuming HGT, this might be indicative of some kind of preferential ‘compatibility’ of R-bodies with *Holospirales*. For example, we may hypothesize that R-bodies are advantageous in symbionts of *Paramecium* and other ciliates, considering the cases of *Bealeia*, ‘*Caedimonas*’, *Caedibacter*, and even ‘*Ca. Finniella inopinata*’, which, while hosted by the cercozoan *Viridiraptor*, has a close relative associated with the ciliate *Euplotes* (Boscaro et al., 2019). Also considering the extremely high phylogenetic proximity of Reb proteins of *Holospirales* (Figure 3), a plausible alternative explanation is that R-bodies could have been ancestral in *Holospirales*, then loss in multiple sublineages, thus mirroring many chromosome-encoded functions presented above. Accordingly, an intriguing role of R-bodies in the evolution of host interaction and association in the *Holospirales* could be suggested (Figure 5). Further analyses, in particular investigating the presence and role of R-bodies in *Bealeia* and ‘*Ca. Finniella inopinata*’ could provide a better understanding of their evolutionary role for the *Holospirales*.

Among the very few detected differences between the two *Bealeia* genomes, noteworthy are those pertaining to mobile and extrachromosomal elements, such as transposases and plasmids. The exposition of those elements and their potential role as sources of functional genomic variability indicates a dynamic nature of the *Bealeia* genomes, suggesting that, despite the overall trends discussed above, these bacteria are not one-way evolving towards a deeper genome reduction and host dependence.

To sum up, the newly obtained genomes of *Bealeia* allowed to stabilize the reconstructed phylogeny of *Holospirales*, thus being instrumental in further investigating their evolutionary history. Accordingly, we infer that genome reduction and evolution of host adaptation occurred at least partly independently in different sublineages. With its larger genomic repertoire, *Bealeia* is likely more ‘reminiscent’ of the ancestral state of the *Holospiraceae*, and possibly of the whole order. From

a comparative perspective, those findings are reminiscent of convergent evolutionary patterns delineated within the *Rickettsiales* (Castelli, Nardi, et al., 2022), but with relevant differences, partly relatable to the more recent origin of *Holospirales* (Muñoz-Gómez et al., 2019). Our investigations indicate that R-bodies are much more widespread in *Holospirales* than previously recognized. Whether this unique feature among professional symbionts is ancestral or the result of a recent HGT is still unclear (Figure 5), and their functional and evolutionary impacts, including whether they may be actual determinants of a killer trait (Schrallhammer & Schweikert, 2009), are still undetermined. We thus underline the relevance of further experimental and genomic investigations on *Holospirales*, to shed on the features and evolutionary trends of professional symbionts in general. These should ideally include the production of high-quality genome sequences, instrumental in particular for investigations on relevant plasmid-encoded components and functions such as the R-bodies.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Genome sequencing and assembly

The sample preparation, genome sequencing and assembly procedures are described in detail in the Supplementary materials (Supplementary Text 1; Supplementary Table 4). Briefly, shotgun sequencing was attained on an Illumina HiSeq X machine from whole-genome amplification (WGA) products of US_BI 1511 (45,068,581 pairs of 150 bp reads) and US_BI 111111 *P. biaurelia* cells (37,367,684 pairs of 150 bp reads). For each sample, the whole set of Illumina reads was preliminarily assembled using SPAdes 3.6 (Bankevich et al., 2012). Then, the Blobology pipeline (Kumar et al., 2013) was applied, to separate contigs belonging to *Bealeia* from those of *Paramecium* and other bacteria, based on GC content, sequencing coverage, and sequence homology. This set of contigs was manually checked and revised. In parallel, the WGA products were subjected to multiple runs of long-read sequencing with the Oxford Nanopore Technology, using the Rapid

FIGURE 5 (A) Two alternative reconstructions of the evolutionary steps leading to presence/absence in the extant *Holospirales* along a cladogram based on the full species tree (Figure 1). A scenario of ‘ancient single acquisition’ of the *reb* genes (left), determinants of the R-bodies, followed by multiple losses in those *Holospirales* devoid of such genes, would be consistent with phylogenetic proximity and accordance with the organismal phylogeny of the Reb proteins in *Holospirales* (Figure 4A; Supplementary Figure 11). Conversely, ‘multiple recent acquisitions’ (right) would be congruous with the fact that, being plasmid-encoded, *reb* genes are highly likely to be involved in HGT events. In each reconstruction, along each branch, the inferred presence/absence of the genes are shown in red/black, respectively, while HGT events and losses are shown by encircled arrows and crosses, respectively. (B) Generalized scheme showing the main steps of the action exerted in *Paramecium* by the R-bodies of the *Holospirales* bacterium ‘*Caedimonas*’ and of the unrelated gammaproteobacterium *Caedibacter taeniospiralis* (based on Schrallhammer & Schweikert, 2009). When a bacterium carrying R-bodies is released through the host cytoproct and ingested by a symbiont-free sensitive host, the acidification of the digestive vacuoles will lead to the unrolling of the R-bodies, followed by the release of not fully characterized lethal toxins. It is conceivable that at least partly analogous mechanisms may be involved in the interaction of *Bealeia* or other *Holospirales* bearing *reb* genes with the respective hosts, including but not limited to *Paramecium* and other ciliates.

Barcoding Kit (SQK-RBK004), or the Ligation Sequencing kit (SQK-LSK109) with the Native Barcoding Expansion (EXP-NBD104). For each sample, the total long reads were combined, and selected for size and quality using Filtlong v0.2.0 (<https://github.com/rwick/Filtlong>). Finally, for each strain selected short reads (i.e., those mapping on selected contigs [Langmead & Salzberg, 2012]) and filtered long reads were assembled using Unicycler 0.4.8 (Wick et al., 2017), followed by manual curation (Castelli et al., 2019). BUSCO v3 (Simão et al., 2015) was used to assess the completeness of the genomes based on the *Proteobacteria* dataset.

Genome sequence comparisons within *Bealeia* and annotation

The ANI between the two complete genomes of *Bealeia* was determined using an ANI calculator (<http://enve-omics.ce.gatech.edu/ani/>). MUMer4 (Marçais et al., 2018) was used to obtain (with the built-in NUCmer) the whole genome alignments between the two symbionts.

The assembled *Bealeia* genomes were annotated using Prokka v.1.13.7 (Seemann, 2014) with *--rfam* option. The functional annotations were manually curated by inspecting blastp results of predicted CDSs on NCBI nr and a custom database including all annotated proteins belonging to *Holosporales*. Circular genome plots were created using the DNAPlotter (Carver et al., 2009) web server.

Metabolic predictions and comparisons

The COGs were predicted in the two *Bealeia* and other selected *Holosporales* using the NCBI pipeline (Galperin et al., 2015). The repertoire of COGs was directly compared among those organisms, and manually inspected in comparison with the annotation, using the BioCyc (Karp et al., 2019) and KEGG (Kanehisa et al., 2016) databases as references for metabolic pathway reconstruction. Additionally, to investigate the relationship between the number of COGs and the respective genome size, a linear regression analysis was performed. The analysis was carried out using the *lm()* function in R, which is specifically designed for fitting linear models.

Phylogenomic analyses

For phylogenomic analyses, a set of 17 published genome assemblies of *Holosporales* bacteria was selected, plus, as an outgroup, six other *Alphaproteobacteria* ('full organism dataset'). Given the proximity of the two *Bealeia paramacronuclearis* (as per the ANI), only the US_BI 1511 strain was employed.

Single-copy orthologs were identified using Orthofinder 2.3.11 (Emms & Kelly, 2019) on the respective annotated proteins. Subsequently, each ortholog was aligned using Muscle 3.8.31 (Edgar, 2004) and polished with Gblocks 0.91b (Talavera & Castresana, 2007) with default settings. Finally, all orthologs were concatenated together (72 genes, 12,623 total positions).

The optimal amino acid substitution model for the alignment was determined with ProtTest 3.4.2 (Darriba et al., 2011). Afterward, maximum likelihood (ML) and Bayesian inference (BI) trees were inferred, respectively using RAxML (1000 bootstrap pseudo-replicates) (Stamatakis, 2015) and MrBayes 3.2.6 (Ronquist et al., 2012), as described previously (Castelli et al., 2021). Finally, to reduce potential artefacts due to long-branch attraction, the four genomes presenting the longest branches among *Holosporaceae* (namely two '*Ca. Cytomitobacter* spp.', '*Ca. Nesciobacter*', and '*Ca. Gromoviella*') in the initial dataset were removed from the concatenated alignment of the 72 orthologs ('no fast-evolving organisms dataset'), and ML and BI trees were inferred on the modified dataset as described above.

Analyses of gene content variation

We used the Count software (Csűrös, 2010) to evaluate the rates of gain, loss, expansion and contraction rates across homologue gene families (employing from COGs) in the *Holosporales* tree. Following the Count manual, we optimized rates under a gain-loss-duplication model, setting a Poisson family size distribution at root, with the following rate variations across families (Edge length = 4 categories; Loss rate = 1 categories; Gain rate = 1 category; Duplication rate = 4 categories). The convergence threshold on likelihood was set to 0.1, with a maximum of 100 optimization rounds. The gene family history by posterior probabilities was then reconstructed.

Phylogenetic analyses Tlc and BioY transporters

For the phylogeny of Tlc nucleotide translocases, we started from the dataset by (Castelli, Nardi, et al., 2022), initially obtained by the addition of alpha-proteobacterial sequences to a subset of the sequences analysed in a previous study (Major et al., 2017). The amino acid sequences of the Tlc translocases in the analysed *Holosporales* (using *Bealeia* US_BI 1511 only as a representative for this species) were obtained by inspecting blastp hits with, as queries, the *Bealeia* sequences identified during the manual curation of the annotation. The whole set of sequences was de novo aligned with MAFFT 7.475 L-INS-i (Kato & Standley, 2013), and trimmed with

BMGE 1.12 (Criscuolo & Gribaldo, 2010) with the BLOSUM30 matrix. Following Major and colleagues (Major et al., 2017), phylogeny was then inferred with IQ-TREE 1.6.12 (Nguyen et al., 2015) with the LG + C60 model, performing 1000 ultrafast bootstraps (Minh et al., 2013) and SH-aLRT with 1000 replicates.

For the phylogeny of the biotin transporter BioY, a blastp search was performed (with the *Bealeia* sequence as a query) on a representative selection of alphaproteobacterial sequences from a previous study (Castelli, Nardi, et al., 2022) with a 1e-5 threshold, as well as on the other here investigated *Holospirales*. Amino acid sequences were then aligned and trimmed with MAFFT and BMGE as described above, and phylogeny was inferred with IQ-TREE, employing ModelFinder (Kalyanamoorthy et al., 2017) for model selection, and performing 1000 ultrafast bootstraps and SH-aLRT with 1000 replicates.

Phylogeny of the biotin synthesis genes

An approach previously set up and employed for amino acid and nucleotide synthesis was followed (Castelli, Nardi, et al., 2022). Specifically, we started from egg-nog COGs (Huerta-Cepas et al., 2019) predicted with egg-nog-mapper 2.0.6 (Cantalapiedra et al., 2021) on *Holospirales* and the alphaproteobacterial + outgroup dataset by Castelli and colleagues. From the reference pathway of biotin synthesis of BioCyc (Karp et al., 2019), only the six biotin-specific genes were considered (i.e., *fab* genes shared with fatty acid synthesis were discarded). For each selected gene, the Biocyc reference sequence was queried by blastp against the amino acid sequences of the dataset, and results were manually inspected, to identify orthologs and select corresponding eggNOGs (*bioC*: COG0500@1; *bioF*: COG0156@2; *bioA*: COG0161@2; *bioD*: COG0132@2; *bioB*: COG0132@2; while *bioH* was discarded from the following analyses as no orthologs could be identified among *Holospirales*).

The corresponding amino acid sequences were aligned with MAFFT, trimmed with BMGE as described above, and single-gene trees were obtained with IQTREE. Results were manually revised to remove short/poorly aligned sequences and paralogs. To get more phylogenetically informative datasets and thus robust and reliable phylogenetic inferences, the sequences were then concatenated together with AMAS (Borowiec, 2016). Before concatenation, we discarded those organisms presenting less than 50% of the analysed genes, bearing too limited phylogenetic information and deemed as probable 'false positives' for the presence of the pathway. Finally, a phylogenetic tree was inferred from the concatenated alignment with IQTREE, employing ModelFinder as described above.

Phylogenetic analyses of Reb proteins

For the phylogeny of the Reb proteins (components of R-bodies), we started from the dataset by Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2021). To minimize false negatives, each amino acid sequence from such dataset was queried on each *Holospirales* bacterium, and combined hits were manually inspected, thus selecting the putative Reb sequences. Considering that, similarly to other bacteria (Schrallhammer & Schweikert, 2009), *reb* genes were found to be plasmidic in *Bealeia*, and that, differently from the chromosomes, plasmids are not equivalent in the two *Bealeia* strains (see Results), also the second strain (i.e., US_BI 11III1) was included in this analysis. All the retrieved sequences were de novo aligned with MAFFT, trimmed with BMGE, and phylogeny was inferred with IQ-TREE employing ModelFinder, as described above.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Michele Giovannini: Data curation (lead); formal analysis (equal); investigation (lead); software (lead); visualization (lead); writing – original draft (lead). **Giulio Petroni**: Conceptualization (equal); funding acquisition (lead); resources (lead); supervision (equal); writing – review and editing (equal). **Michele Castelli**: Conceptualization (lead); formal analysis (equal); investigation (equal); resources (supporting); supervision (lead); visualization (supporting); writing – original draft (equal); writing – review and editing (lead).

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Sequences obtained in this work are publicly accessible under the NCBI BioProject PRJNA979986: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA979986>.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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